

INTERNATIONAL YOUTH DIPLOMATIC COOPERATION (IYDC)

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Overview: this article mainly concentrates on collaborative efforts among younger generation worldwide to engage in diplomacy and address global challenges.

Key words: 1. Collaboration 2. Resolution Papers 3. Model United Nations (MUN) 4. Youth Diplomatic Conference (YDC) 5. Committees Needing Collaboration 6. Diplomatic Enhancement 7. Networking 8. Cultural Exchange 9. First International Diplomatic Conference in Uzbekistan 10. Future Diplomats
Why do we need this conference?

1. Many diplomatic conferences, such as the Model United Nations (MUN) and the Youth Diplomatic Conference (YDC), emphasize competition over collaboration. These conferences separate students into different blocks in the part where they should write resolution papers, meaning that they are forced to compete against each other to submit a preferable resolution paper. It is undeniably true that in the process within the blocks, delegates have a chance to collaborate, but the main purpose has always been different. So by having IYDC, we allow delegates to work with each other and combine their brilliance into one project so that they can come up with an all in favor resolution paper.

2. There are several committees that cannot fit into either MUN or YDC due to their requirement for collaboration: Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa (BRICS+), African Union (AU), European Union (EU), Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Mexico, Indonesia, Nigeria, Turkey (MINT), Group of Twenty (G20), Colombia, Indonesia, Vietnam, Egypt, Turkey, South Africa (CIVETS), Union of South American Nations (UNASUR), Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), India, Brazil, South Africa (IBSA Dialogue Forum), Next Eleven (N-11), and Association of Southern Asian Nations (ASEAN). IYDC is the solution for such organizations that are in need of other collaborative environments for conferences.

3. Not only is the collaborative atmosphere at IYDC beneficial, but its offer of diplomatic enhancement can be encouraging to the future diplomats of our nation. In the IYDC conference, students are able to experience various stages of the business, science, education, and international relations sectors' necessities: knowledge exchange, networking and relationship building, innovation and problem solving, economics and business opportunities, policy and advocacy,

building community and solidarity, professional development, cultural exchange and understanding, and strategic planning and vision.

4. The fine and final initiative of IYDC conference creation is to build a strong and sustainable, and most importantly, THE FIRST international diplomatic conference in Uzbekistan. This breakthrough can strengthen Uzbekistan's international connections with other countries abroad, as the main reason behind IYDC is to allow youth to cooperate under international diplomatic committees so that they can have deep insights into the policy, economy, and culture of the particular country that they are representing. This is a once-in-a-lifetime opportunity for future diplomats in Uzbekistan to experience the collaborative nature of diplomacy.

Rules and regulations

Team members & Roles and responsibilities

- **Supreme Coordinator (Chairperson):** Coordinate committee activities and oversee the conference planning process.
- **Secretary-General:** Manage the process of communication and documentation.
- **Fiscal Wizard (Treasurer):** Responsible for financial matters including budgeting and fundraising.
- **Public Relations Officer:** Manage participant registrations and promote the conference.
- **Logistics Coordinator:** Arrange logistical needs including venue, materials.

Format and Structure

A. Type of conference

- International Youth Diplomatic Cooperation

B. Committees

- Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa (BRICS+)
- African Union (AU)
- European Union (EU)
- Mexico, Indonesia, Nigeria, Turkey (MINT)
- Association of Southern Asian Nations (ASEAN)

C. Duration

- One to Two-day conference

Rules and Procedures

A. Drafting rules

- **Debate Format:** Formal rules for speech, points, and motions.

- **Points and Motions:** point of order, point of personal privilege, point of inquiry, motion to adjourn, motion to suspend debate.

- **Voting procedures:** Voting methods (roll call; present or present and voting, show of placards)

B. Guidelines

- **Delegate preparation:** proper research into the given country's politics, topic background and international relations/role with other nations within the committee and write the position paper accordingly.

Conference materials

- **Delegate handbook:** include rules, procedures and background guides.

- **Badges and Placards:** while badges are for representing particular committee, placards are for particular country.

- **Certificates and Awards:** The certificate of participation, The certificate of volunteering, the award of the best delegate, the award of the best supreme coordinator, The award of the best resolution paper.

Training sessions

- **Workshops:** inform attenders about rules, procedures and process of the conference.

- **Briefing sessions:** introduction session for staff and volunteers.

Conference executions

- **Opening ceremony:** welcome opening speeches from key organizers and guests.

- **Closing ceremony:** announce awards, close the ceremony with president of the conference's speech.

- **After party:** organize party event afterwards of closing ceremony.

Key regulations to bear in mind

1. The resolution paper is written within only one block of a particular committee, with delegates within that committee working towards achieving solutions for global issues for all member countries. In addition to this, delegates can enhance their cooperation skills in diplomacy while writing the resolution paper. The award for the best resolution paper is decided by the president of the conference and presented to the most cooperative and active committee. The resolution paper writers decide the main submitter and co-submitter according to their leadership qualities by voting, so that the award is presented to the legacy holder (the main submitter) of a particular committee. The resolution papers of all participant countries are checked for plagiarism, and the percentage should not be higher than 15%. The resolution papers can have new

and creative formats as long as they stay formal, giving the opportunity for delegates to express their creative imaginations in a cooperative atmosphere. The supreme coordinator is responsible for not only making amendments to the resolution paper, but he also has the capability of having arguments to challenge the main submitter and co-submitter's defending skills of their resolution paper. There is only one award for the best resolution paper in the whole conference.

2. In order to have a long-lasting conference, there is a position for the main submitter, which was earlier mentioned: the legacy holder. In the following IYDC conferences, the delegate who achieves that position will be asked to attend next year's conference to present his throne to the next legacy holder to keep the tradition ongoing.

3. There are 6 sessions in the conference other than general speaking lists, in which 4 sessions should be devoted to addressing solutions to the issue, and 2 sessions are for resolution paper writing and making amendments. The first four sessions are always in moderated caucus, while the last two sessions are in unmoderated caucus, allowing delegates to combine their brilliance and ideas into one resolution paper. It is highly requested from delegates to deeply understand the issue itself before the conference so that the first four sessions are only dedicated to finding solutions to the given agenda and not repeatedly giving stage speeches about the problem itself. The last two sessions should make sure all the countries in committees are involved in the procedure; otherwise, their likelihood of getting the best resolution paper lowers.

4. The number of countries should not exceed 15, as it is hard to gather more than 15 countries into one collaborative resolution paper writing process. In this case, the possibility of each country's representatives' active participation in every session will greatly increase. Unlike other conferences, IYDC values the active participation of each delegate, as all countries should meet their expectations by allowing other country delegates to have a glance at a particular country's situation regarding the presented problem. The duration for unmoderated and moderated caucus could be a maximum of 30 minutes; this will allow a maximum of 15 delegates to have their part in all sessions with 1/1.5/2minute stage speeches.

Future diplomats! Diplomacy is not just about competition and having hot debates at conferences; it is also about collaboration and gathering various brilliant ideas into one team-working atmosphere. That is why IYDC offers passionate future diplomats the opportunity to challenge their team-building, cooperation, and leadership qualities!

Quotations:

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